

MONITORING THE EFFECT OF DAMAGE IN WOVEN FABRIC LAMINATES

C. Kyriazoglou^{*}, B.H. Le-Page⁺ and F.J. Guild^{*}

^{*}*Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Bristol, Bristol BS8 1TR, UK*

⁺*School of Engineering, University of Surrey, Guildford, Surrey GU2 7XH, UK*

ABSTRACT

This paper explores the use of vibration damping as a potential non-destructive test method to detect early cracks in a woven fabric laminate. The experimental work consists of measurements of energy loss during the resonant vibration of woven fabric laminates and measurement of the Specific Damping Capacity (SDC). The results demonstrate the sensitivity of SDC to the presence of low levels of damage. The level of damage present in woven laminates can be related to both the value of specific damping capacity and the dependence of specific damping capacity on the amplitude of the vibration. The results support the concept of monitoring changes in SDC values in order to detect successfully preliminary damage in woven fabric laminates before the material experiences other (more potentially damaging) failure modes.

KEYWORDS: Woven laminate, specific damping capacity, structural integrity, matrix cracking

INTRODUCTION

Woven fabric laminates are receiving more attention as potential materials for engineering applications due to their excellent drapability, allowing for complex shapes to be made, and resistance to impact damage. Despite these benefits, their wider use is restricted by a lack of understanding of issues relating to their structural integrity. Quantification and modelling of damage accumulation possesses inherent difficulties due mainly to the complexity of the fiber architecture. The detection of damage in woven fabric laminates is a vital step in allowing their wider use in critical applications. This work is a part of a wider programme which aims to develop sound physical models to describe the relationship between damage and residual properties in woven fabric composites, and to develop proposals for a non-destructive testing tool to monitor damage in service.

Modal analysis has been investigated by several workers as a potential technique for structural health monitoring in composite laminates. The method is based on the change in local stiffness arising from a defect, which causes change in the frequency response of the structure. The method can be applied either using ambient vibrations in structures or forced vibrations using an actuator. This can be considered as an extension of the coin-tap test traditionally used for metallic structures [1]. The method has been recently developed by Gibson and his co-workers using fast analytical techniques [2]. The sensitivity of this method, particularly for the detection of delaminations, has recently been reviewed [3]. However, early damage in carbon fibre reinforced laminates does not result in measurable changes in values of stiffness [4]; modal analysis would not be expected to detect such damage. This paper explores the use of measurement of Specific Damping Capacity as a potential tool for successful detection of such early damage. Initial tests were carried out using GFRP continuous cross-ply laminates where the damage could be easily detected and quantified. Woven GFRP and CFRP laminates were then investigated.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The dynamic properties of the materials were measured using the steady state method since this method leads to the most precise measurements of specific damping capacity and has been shown to be sensitive to very small cracks in composite laminates [5]. However, it should be noted that preliminary experiments were carried out using both the band-width and free decay methods [6], and overall reasonably good agreement was found between results from the steady state method and these other methods.

In the steady state dynamic method, beams are vibrated in free-free flexure in their first mode of resonant vibration, as shown in figure 1. Two thin wires are used to support the vibrating beam, at the nodal positions. Magnets are attached at each end of the beam which move in the field of static coils, driving the vibration. A sinusoidal input signal is produced from a frequency generator. The oscillating signal is amplified through a power amplifier and current flows to the two coils, which are connected in series with each other, and the power amplifier. Current flowing into the magnetic fields of the two end magnets produces a sinusoidal force that drives the beam symmetrically. At resonant vibration the maximum displacement, at the centre of the beam, is measured using a laser device. At resonance, values of resonant frequency, maximum displacement and current flowing into the coils are recorded. Using previous calibration of the magnet-coil pairs, the energy input to the system is calculated from the measured input current.

Dynamic tests were carried out both in ambient conditions and in a vacuum chamber, at around 0.01 Bar. An effect of air damping was found; the effect varied for the different laminates whose results are presented here. For clarity in this paper, all dynamic results presented are those obtained from testing in the vacuum chamber.

Figure 1. Schematics of Steady State Method

ANALYSIS

The classical solution of the wave equation has been well documented by Guild & Adams [7]. However a number of key features should be emphasized. Making the usual assumptions for a Bernoulli-Euler beam, the equation of motion for free-free lateral vibration is:

$$EI \frac{\partial^4 u}{\partial x^4} + \rho A \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

where: E = Dynamic flexural modulus,
 I = beam second moment of area,
 x = distance along beam length,
 u = transverse displacement,
 ρ = density of beam material,
 A = cross sectional area of beam,
 t = time.

Having obtained the experimental values of resonant frequency, f_{res} , of the vibrating beam in its first mode of resonant vibration, the value of the wavelength number λ including the rotary inertia J of the end magnets [7] and measured the period T of the resonant vibration, flexural modulus, E_{flex} , is given by:

$$E_{flex} = \frac{m}{\pi} \left(\frac{2\pi}{T} \right)^2 \left(\frac{l}{\lambda} \right)^4 \quad (2)$$

where: λ = wavelength number,
 T = period of resonant vibration.

The energy stored by the beam in bending, U is given by:

$$U = \frac{E_{flex} I}{2} \int_0^l \left(\frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial x^2} \right)^2 dx \quad (3)$$

It is assumed that the energy stored by the beam in shear is negligible.

From equation (3), using integration by parts, it may be shown that U is an implicit function of the maximum lateral vibration of the beam in its first mode of resonant vibration, and its resonant frequency. The energy input, ΔU , is calculated from the previously measured calibration factors of the coil-magnet pairs, the current flowing in the coils and the maximum displacement of the beam. Thus the Specific Damping Capacity, ψ , can be calculated using:

$$\psi = \frac{\Delta U}{U} \quad (4)$$

MATERIALS

The continuous fibre Glass Fibre Reinforced Polymer (GFRP) composites were prepared using Astor Stag epoxy resin system with a MNA Hardener curing agent and a K61B Accelerator. The reinforcement was E-glass continuous fibers with a density of 2.56 gm/cm^3 . Cross-ply laminated plates, $[0^\circ/90^\circ]_s$ and $[90^\circ/0^\circ]_s$, were prepared in the laboratory using a filament winding wet lay-up process, resulting in an approximate volume fraction of 40 %. This volume fraction was measured and found to be about 40%. The ply thickness was around 0.4 mm, giving a total laminate thickness of around 1.6 mm. For the Woven GFRP systems, the resin matrix was a Shell Epikote 828 epoxy resin system with a MNA curing agent and K61B accelerator. The fiber reinforcement was a Fothergill Engineered Fabrics Ltd Y0227 E-glass continuous eight-harness satin weave fabric. The cloth had an approximate weight of 297 gm/m^2 and the density of the E-glass fibers was taken as 2.56 gm/cm^3 . The laminates were prepared in the laboratory using a similar hand lay-up process used for the cross-ply laminates, with much care taken to ensure true balance in the laminate with respect to the warp and weft directions. The volume fraction achieved was around 40%. The Woven CFRP systems had a Ventico M7750 epoxy resin system and the fiber reinforcement was a T300 carbon fiber continuous five-harness satin weave cloth.

All laminates investigated in this study were in the form of simple beam coupons. The types of lay-ups of the laminated coupons varied. The lay-ups and materials tested were: $[0^\circ/90^\circ]_s$ continuous GFRP; $[90^\circ/0^\circ]_s$ continuous GFRP; woven $[0^\circ,90^\circ]$ GFRP reinforced with 6 layers of 8 harness satin weave; woven $[0^\circ,90^\circ]$ CFRP reinforced with 4 layers of 5 harness satin weave. The GFRP beams were about 2 mm thick, 12.5 mm wide and 200 mm long. The CFRP beams were about 1.6 mm thick, 25 mm wide and 230 mm long.

MECHANICAL TESTING

Damage was introduced into the cross ply continuous GFRP coupons by quasi static loading, using a strain rate of 0.1 mm/sec. The effect of damage to a series of coupons was investigated; each coupon was loaded in tension up to a different maximum strain in order to obtain a series of increasing crack densities. The quasi-static loading caused transverse cracking in the 90° plies. The cracks usually extended across the full width and thickness of the ply and the crack density increased with increasing strain. The typical appearance of the cracks at 1.9% strain for $[90^\circ/0^\circ]_s$ laminate is shown in Figure 2; cracks in both 90° plies are visible. The cracks are approximately evenly spaced along the beam.

Figure 2 Plan View showing Transverse Cracking in 90° Plies in $[90/0]_s$ GFRP beam

Quasi-static loading was also used to introduce damage into the woven cross ply GFRP coupons. The damage in the woven cross ply GFRP coupons was observed using both optical microscopy and scanning electron microscopy (SEM). It was found that damage was initiated as matrix cracking in the transverse tows and was mainly concentrated in the crimp area. However, for the woven cross ply CFRP coupons, fatigue loading was required to allow investigation of varying levels of damage. The CFRP coupons were subjected to an increasing number of cycles of fatigue loading in tension, using an R ratio of 0.1, with maximum load at 60% of their static failure load.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

CONTINUOUS GFRP BEAMS: The dynamic properties of the continuous cross-ply GFRP laminates were examined with respect to the measured crack density. As expected, the effects were far greater for the $[90^{\circ}/0^{\circ}]_s$ beams when the transverse cracking was in the outer plies of the beam. The values of dynamic flexural modulus for the damaged beams were reduced, as expected, but were not dependent on the amplitude of the vibration for both undamaged and damaged beams. Values of specific damping capacity increased with increasing damage; for the damaged beams, the measured values were found to be dependent on vibration amplitude. Examples of this behaviour for a $[90^{\circ}/0^{\circ}]_s$ undamaged beam and damaged beams with different crack densities are shown in Figure 3.

The dependence of specific damping capacity on crack density with crack density was quantified with respect to a given input current or energy input to the system. The value of input current used was 100 mA, corresponding to a maximum displacement of around 0.8 mm for the undamaged beams. The values of specific damping capacity for the different beams were normalised with respect to the measured value of specific damping capacity for that beam in its undamaged state. These normalised values, $R(\text{SDC})$ are shown in Figure 4 as a function of crack density for both $[90^{\circ}/0^{\circ}]_s$ and $[0^{\circ}/90^{\circ}]_s$ beams.

Figure 3. Comparison of values for SDC for undamaged and damaged $[90^{\circ}/0^{\circ}]_s$ continuous GFRP coupons

Figure 4. Variation of normalised ratio of SDC, R(SDC), with transverse crack density for continuous GFRP cross-ply laminates

The results in Figure 4 show the expected behaviour for the different laminates. When the cracks are in the outer plies, $[90^{\circ}/0^{\circ}]_s$ laminates, the values of specific damping capacity are far more sensitive to crack density; the values appear directly proportional to the crack density. When the cracks are in the inner plies, $[0^{\circ}/90^{\circ}]_s$ laminates, the values of specific damping capacity show a small but significant increase for low crack density but the values, when compared for equal energy input, appear unaffected by higher crack densities.

Figure 5. Amplitude dependence Z, with transverse crack density for continuous GFRP cross-ply laminates

A further attempt was made to quantify these results with respect to the observed change in amplitude dependence with increasing crack density observed in the results (see Figure 3). As a first approximation, the variation of specific damping capacity with maximum displacement for a given beam was fitted to a linear trend line. The values of the slope of the trend line, Z , were then plotted with respect to the crack density. The results are shown in Figure 5; results are included for both $[90^{\circ}/0^{\circ}]_s$ and $[0^{\circ}/90^{\circ}]_s$ beams.

The results in Figure 5 show a clear increase in the magnitude of the amplitude dependence with crack density for the $[90^{\circ}/0^{\circ}]_s$ beams, when the cracks are in the outer plies. No significant amplitude dependence was found for the $[0^{\circ}/90^{\circ}]_s$ beams. Although there is significant scatter in the results for the $[90^{\circ}/0^{\circ}]_s$ beams, it is clear that there is increase in amplitude dependence with increasing damage; the nature of the trend is not clear from the results in Figure 5. However, these results do indicate that the magnitude of the amplitude dependence of specific damping capacity could be used in a tool for monitoring structural integrity of composite laminates.

WOVEN GFRP BEAMS: The dynamic properties of the woven GFRP beams were measured for different expected levels of damage obtained by subjecting the specimens to different levels of maximum strain in the quasi-static tests. The values of specific damping capacity for the different beams were normalised with respect to the measured value for the beam in its undamaged state. The results are shown in Figure 6. These results may be compared with the results for the cross-ply laminates shown in Figure 4 where the damage could be accurately measured. For the woven laminate subjected to strain exceeding about 0.6%, the value of normalised ratio of specific damping capacity is around 1.75, which corresponds to a transverse crack density in the outer plies of the continuous cross-ply laminates of around 100 m^{-1} (figure 4). No increase in the value of normalised ratio of specific damping capacity is found for the woven laminates for increasing imposed maximum strain. This behaviour can be described from the continuous cross-ply results; no further increase in $R(\text{SDC})$ is found for increasing crack density for the $[0^{\circ}/90^{\circ}]_s$. Therefore the behaviour of the woven cross-ply laminates shown in Figure 6 indicates that the initial damage in the quasi-static loading is in the outer plies, but further damage, at increasing imposed strain, is in the inner plies. This hypothesis is supported by examining the amplitude dependence of the results; the results are shown in Figure 7. The amount of amplitude dependence for strain exceeding about 0.6% is comparable to the amount found for the $[90^{\circ}/0^{\circ}]_s$ laminates at crack density of around 100 m^{-1} (figure 4). The amount of amplitude dependence does not increase after higher applied strain.

Figure 6. Variation of $R(\text{SDC})$ for woven GFRP cross ply laminates with increasing maximum strain

Figure 7. Amplitude dependence with increasing maximum strain for Woven GFRP cross ply laminates

Figure 8. Variation of R(SDC) with increasing number of cycles of fatigue for woven CFRP cross ply laminates

WOVEN CFRP LAMINATES: Several woven CFRP beams were subjected to different numbers of fatigue cycles. The normalised ratios of specific damping capacity for five beams are shown in Figure 8. Although the results in figure 8 show considerable scatter, the overall trend is clear; increasing values of specific damping capacity arise from increasing fatigue damage. These results indicate that the amount of damage in the outer plies increases with increasing fatigue cycles. This hypothesis is confirmed by examination of the amplitude dependence; the results are shown in Figure 9. Increasing amplitude dependence is found for increasing levels of fatigue cycles; this indicates that damage continues to accumulate in the outer plies and may also be occurring in the inner plies.

The maximum number of fatigue cycles survived by the different beams varied. Observing Figures 8 and 9, it can be seen that specimen F24 survived a high number of cycles. The results for this beam were examined in more detail. The value of specific damping capacity for the highest number of cycles does not appear to follow the steady trend shown by results from the lower number of cycles. This is clear in Figure 8 for the value of specific damping capacity, and is indicated in Figure 9 for the amount of amplitude dependence. The damaged state of this specimen has been examined in detail using resin burn-off and de-ply; longitudinal tow fracture has been observed. Tow failure is the expected final catastrophic failure mechanism in woven fabric composites [8]. The changing trend of values of specific damping capacity for this beam could be attributable to the onset of tow failure.

Figure 9. Amplitude dependence with increasing number of cycles of fatigue for woven CFRP cross-ply laminates

CONCLUDING REMARKS

A series of test coupons were considered and tested in both their undamaged and damaged states. Increased values of Specific Damping Capacity were found for all damaged coupons, whilst values for flexural modulus demonstrate less sensitivity to increasing damage. Values of SDC for the $[90^{\circ}/0^{\circ}]_s$ GFRP coupons were found to increase for increasing crack density; coupons with a $[0^{\circ}/90^{\circ}]_s$ lay-up demonstrate less sensitivity. That is expected, since only the outer layers would degrade as crack density increased and the dynamic behavior of vibrating beams is largely defined by the characteristics of the outer layer. Increasing normalised damping values in relation to damage levels were observed for the woven cross ply GFRP 8HSW test coupons and the Woven cross ply CFRP 5HSW coupons. Overall, alteration in dynamic behaviour could be conveniently utilized to signify the intensity and perhaps the location and type of accumulated damage. These experimental observations strongly support the concept of monitoring changes in SDC values in order to detect successfully preliminary damage in woven fabric laminates before the material experiences other (more potentially damaging) failure modes.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS: This work was funded by EPSRC. The authors gratefully acknowledge valuable discussions with Professor P A Smith and Dr S L Ogin, University of Surrey, and with Professor R D Adams, University of Bristol.

REFERENCES

1. Cawley, P. and Adams, R.D., 'The mechanics of the coin-tap method of non-destructive testing', *J Sound & Vibration* Vol 122 (1988) pg 299
2. Gibson, R.F., 'Modal vibration response measurements for characterisation of composite materials and structures', *Composites Science & Tech.* Vol 60 (2000) pg 2769
3. Zou, Y., Tong, L. and Steven, G.P., 'Vibration-based model-dependent damage (delamination) identification and health monitoring for composite structures – A review', *J Sound & Vibration* Vol 230 (2000) pg 357
4. Gao, F., Boniface, L., Ogin, S.L., Smith, P.A., and Greaves, R.P., 'Damage accumulation in woven-fabric CFRP laminates under tensile loading: Part 1. Observations of damage accumulation', *Composites Science & Tech.* Vol 59 (1999) pg 123
5. Guild, F.J. and Adams, R.D., 'A new technique for the measurement of the specific damping capacity of beams in flexure', *J Phys. E: Sci. Inst.* Vol 14 (1981) pg 355
6. Thomson, W.T., 'Theory of vibrations with applications', Prentice-Hall, NJ, USA
7. Guild, F.J. and Adams, R.D., 'The detection of cracks in damaged composite materials', *J Phys D: Appl Phys* Vol 14 (1981) pg 1561
8. Belmonte, H.M.S., Manger, C.I.C., Ogin, S.L., Smith, P.A., and Lewin, R., 'Characterisation and modelling of the notched tensile fracture of woven quasi-isotropic GFRP laminates', *Composites Science & Tech.* Vol 61 (2001) pg 585